

Paper 2

LEARNER AUTONOMY: NEED, MEANING, SCOPE AND IMPORTANCE IN THE L2 LEARNING CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT

Modern English classroom has changed very little from teacher centered classroom to the learner centered one. Teacher domination and teacher dependency still persist in the English Language Teaching (ELT) context. From syllabus prescription to the evaluation system, the learner is left with no other choice than to accept and follow what has been decided by the prescribers. Learners' needs and purposes, aptitudes and preferences are seldom considered. It is here we have to think about learner autonomy as alternative remedy or as a redefined process. Learner autonomy, which another way called learner independence, is defined as the ability to take charge of and responsibility for one's own learning. Autonomous learner is one who realizes the limitation of the classroom and seeks every opportunity outside for learning, here watch TV, read books, consult Peers as well as experts, use internet for improving his or her language proficiency. Autonomous learning is cognitive, reflective and strategic. S/He Is intrinsically motivated to involve actively in the teaching learning process as well as self-evaluate himself or herself their learning and its quality. Autonomous learner gradually gets his or her teacher dependency reduced. Autonomous learner follows a purported, systematic, coherent, cognitive and strategic learning approach. S/He attains linguistic competence more by outside resources than inside the classroom. Consequently the learner becomes an efficient communicator with fluency and accuracy. His or her growth and development as a second language learner would be faster than other less motivated learners. Learner autonomy has been hailed as a modern innovative educational concept in its psychological, social, and political perspectives. The concept and practice of learner autonomy widens the scope of second language learning, envisions learners' expertise and also redefines the role of teacher in the teaching learning arena. Self-monitoring helps them see through their strengths and weaknesses. Then they adopt practical measures to rectify the mistakes for further improvised learning. The practitioners can use certain strategies to foster learner autonomy. Bring in the classroom real life situations. The teacher should cease to be an authoritarian, but reassume his or her role as a modern democratic teacher or a facilitator or as a co-learner. Learners must be allowed the freedom of choice with regard to methods, materials or time and pace. Engage them in group activities or project works so that they would enjoy collaborative learning style.

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Thus learners become increasingly independent of the teacher. They turn out to be self-deciding, self-directive and self-evaluative.

Introduction

Democracy is not an abstract idea but a concrete culture and a way of life. Educational democracy means democratic practices to be followed in the educational processes and procedures for the benefit of the learners. Granting freedom to the learners is of paramount importance. This is the philosophical basis of Learner Autonomy which has become the topic of discussion in the educational scenario for the last thirty years. Here we discuss the need, meaning, scope and importance of learner autonomy in the context of L2 learning. Modern democratic learner centered classroom has to replace the classical authoritarian teacher centered classroom. But still the lot of learners is the same. They are still tongue tied listeners. Their needs and purposes, aptitudes and preferences are one to one different. From syllabus prescription to the evaluation system, learners' needs and purposes, aptitudes and preferences must be taken into account. So Learner Autonomy is discussed here as an alternative remedy or as redefined educational process. It is both a philosophy and a practice, an ideological concept as well as a pragmatic procedure. This new concept has been introduced with a view to motivate the learner and to make learning effective.

Need or Why Learner Autonomy:-

It has been often heard hailing that modern classroom teaching has changed from teacher cantered to learner cantered. It is high time we must examine how far virtually the teaching learning process has changed. On closer examination we understand that teacher domination and teacher dependency still persist in the English language teaching (ELT) context. Very little has changed from teacher cantered or syllabus oriented teaching procedures. From syllabus prescription to the evaluation system, the learner is left with no other option than to accept and follow what has been decided by the prescribers and practitioner's one common syllabus has been prescribed for the entire learners of the same standard. The Learners' different needs and purposes, aptitudes and preferences, knowledge and worldview etc. are not considered before syllabus being prepared. They have no choice in the case of material and methods as well. Of course learning is far more important than teaching whereas even in the modern English classroom focus has not shifted from teaching to learning. As all teaching is directed to exam scores, language skill acquisition has been little cared for. The general aim of all language teaching is to foster Learners' language

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proficiency. But still the learners are kept silent listeners. The teacher reads and explains the content without letting students read and thinks for them first. By and large, teacher talk is maximum and learner talk is nil. Learner involvement as well as learner readiness in the teaching learning process is of utmost importance but conveniently forgotten. Learner motivation in the pre, while and post T/L activities is discarded altogether.

The evaluation is also not flexible. A set pattern is implemented which very often doesn't test what skill it ought to. An examination system should test what the learner knows and what he/she ought to know. In fact pen and paper exam is not a perfect tool to evaluate the learner potential. More over the evaluation system doesn't consider individual differences with regard to their needs, purposes, proficiency and preferences. It is here that we ought to think about learner autonomy as an alternative approach or a process for effective learning to take place.

Its Definition and Meaning:-

Learner Autonomy is termed otherwise as learner independence. Henri Hole puts it thus: “Autonomy is the ability to take charge of one's own learning”. An autonomous learner is called independent learner S/He is responsible for his/her own learning. Autonomous learners are intrinsically motivated. The motivated learner exercises outside the classroom and explores every opportunity to acquire linguistic competence. They become aware of the limitations of the teacher and the classroom in imparting maximum exposure to the target language. So they search for more language experience from other resources such as TV, Internet, audio-video materials, books etc. Then their course of learning becomes self-directed. They grow reflective or thinking on the topics of learning slowly but steadily. They develop critical thinking. They learn to manage their learning by self and by collaborating with peer groups.

Autonomous learner purportedly ensures his/her active involvement in the teaching/learning activities. Dynamic learning makes classroom dynamic. Critical thinking they developed enables them evaluate their performance and the quality of learning. Self-evaluation is a highly covetable trait of learning habit that improvises them perpetually. As a result they continue to pursue learning and be persistent in learning. Self-assessment helps them rectify errors and that accelerate further learning.

Autonomous learning doesn't mean to do away with teacher. It doesn't mean to letting them go astray. Autonomous learning is of course well organized and systematic. Their teacher assumes the

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role of a facilitator. The teacher creates a congenial climate for learning. He acts as a democratic teacher. He ceases to be an instructor but becomes rather a co-learner.

It's scope in second language learning:-

Autonomous learning is increasingly discussed in the modern educational realm. Autonomous learning is cognitive learning. The autonomous learner sets goals. Then s/he follows a goal-directed learning pattern. The learner adopts appropriate strategies for achieving the goals. S/He gets deep insights into his/her topic. They make deliberate attempts to get the concepts all the more clear. So autonomous learning is systematic, coherent, cognitive and strategic.

Learners acquire language skills by being exposed maximum to the target language. But our L2 classroom doesn't offer opportunities for target language exposure. Autonomous learner realizes the limitation of English classroom in that regard. S/He goes beyond the classroom and seeks for resources outside. There are innumerable channels for hearing good English. TV and Internet offer ample chances of listening to English through English film, news, commentary, and panel discussion etc. There are a number of free and paid online courses for learning English. By being exposed to good English, the learners become proficient in the language with good accent, fluency and accuracy. Teachers can acquaint them with sources of information and knowledge.

Importance of Fostering Learner Autonomy:-

There is no dearth of resources, especially in an age of internet. So fostering learner autonomy is of paramount importance. The teacher should find it desirable to promote learner autonomy. It lessens the burden and boredom of his job. Rather it redefines the nature and content of teaching and thereby it elevates his/her status as a teacher. The classroom becomes vibrant with dynamic learners. Advance meticulous preparation on the part of learners makes interaction meaningful and standard. Autonomous classroom promotes peer work and group activities. That makes classes interesting as well as informative. The teacher can make use of the autonomous Learners' service to the benefit of the slow learners. It also leads to innovation.

Learner Autonomy is important in its psychological, social and political perspectives. Autonomy means freedom for learning. Freedom accentuates learning and learning brings autonomy. It is both a means and an end in itself. It both a process and a product. Autonomous learner understands it his responsibility to learn. So learner consults peers, groups, experts and the like. Collaborative learning becomes the part of the whole process. Democratization of the educational institutions and

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its social fabric necessitates learner autonomy.

Strategies for Fostering Learner Autonomy:-

Bring in the classroom real life situations. Learners get motivated to interact upon the topics. Teacher should behave as a co-learner rather than an instructor. This will wipe fears away from the minds of the pupils. So learners get motivated to involve themselves in the classroom activities. Learners must be allowed with freedom of choice, materials, methods etc. Freedom of choice makes them responsible learners. Engage them in the group works so that they will enjoy collaborative learning. Encourage learners to pen down their learning experiences. May those experience drafts be published in school blog or the English blog? They will be excited to see their works published. Thereby the learners become aware of their strengths and weaknesses. Self-assessment is invariably finding one's own merits and deficiencies.

Promoting learning by doing is an act of autonomy fostering. By learning to do is the way one gradually attains autonomy. Scaffolding at the initial level when and where it needed is advisable. Then withdraw scaffolding progressively so that they will learn to do things for themselves. Giving assignments and projects periodically is yet another means of fostering autonomy. They will work in groups of miscellaneous students and acquire the lessons of collaborative learning. Grades may be awarded to their academic works so that the learners would be motivated. These are some of the strategies of fostering autonomy.

The Gaps to be Addressed:-

Autonomy helps thrive learning. More motivated learners become autonomous than the less motivated learners. Yet, we have to take into account the individual as well as institutional constraints of promoting autonomy. Those limitations we must address for the promotion of autonomy. The concept fails to explain the role of teachers in an autonomous classroom and outside. A rationale for teacher intervention role of guidance and evaluation is yet to be prepared. Degree of autonomy varies from person to person and from age to age. In other words, autonomy is variable and unstable. Critics opine that autonomy is an idealistic goal rather than a pragmatic module to be followed in the teaching- learning practice. It means that there is gap between conceptualization and actualization of autonomy. Last, but not the least self-direction is misleading good. Self-direction is an outcome of autonomy, but otherwise. Ability for decision making is feasible only on attaining autonomy. At the same time, Learners' self-evaluation has to be

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promoted. Also one must see whether self-evaluation matches competence.

Conclusion:-

Democratization of the classroom cannot be postponed. Allowing learner autonomy is a part of it. It is doubtless to say that autonomy helps learning to thrive. Learner and learning are most important in the education scenario. Learner Autonomy redefines the teacher role in and outside the classroom. The modern democratic teacher assumes the role as facilitator. S/He is teacher researcher. S/He envisions the development of learner potential. Learner Autonomy widens the frame and content of learning.

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